

THE IMPORTANCE OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN ADAPTING TO STUDENT LIFE

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Annotation. The article covers the processes of adaptation of students enrolled in a higher educational institution to student life. It was also mentioned about the possibilities of a healthy lifestyle in the effective acceleration of the adaptation process.

Keywords: adaptation, biological adaptation, social adaptation, tension of mental activity, a healthy lifestyle.

Today it is worthwhile to mention that the existence of two different forms of adaptation, namely biological and social adaptation, is recognized by the general public. Naturally, unlike animals, a person is socially accustomed to new conditions by his nature. However, the biological nature of humanity, which acquires a social character in the process of its historical development, makes it possible to research it as a natural, fundamental factor. Understanding adaptation from a biological (including physiological) point of view consists of a general and private description of the process in which this phenomenon occurs. These descriptions are relevant for the entire system, regardless of the development and organization of the characteristics of the organism.

The adaptation of young people to Student Life is considered a complex process that requires the adaptation of an organism whose social and biological reserves are not sufficiently formed. In the process of adaptation, students face difficulties associated with the transition to a teaching system in the form of Higher Education. These difficulties are explained by:

- 1) transition of the system of continuing education to new forms and methods of educational work, which are sharply different from the stages of the system of continuing education up to higher education (schools of general secondary education, secondary special educational institutions; the conditions created for the organization of educational activities, as well as the specificity of each activity, the approaches of educators;
- 2) The occurrence of specific difficulties when adapting to the student body, in particular, facing a special social environment, overcoming the mental barrier between students and educators;
- 3) the conspicuousness of the difficulties associated with familiarizing yourself with the content of professional activity in the field of specialization as a future specialist.

The main place in adaptation to the educational process in higher educational institutions is clearly manifested by the activities of students of the first stage. That is why the first year of education is called adaptation directly to higher educational institutions.

Higher educational institutions, first of all, provide for the improvement of the special education and behavior of students, which are based on a significant level of self-awareness. The emergence of a need in this regard:

- 1) lack of daily control over daily tasks and their implementation;

2) explained by the presence of great freedom in the conduct of independent work for students and the establishment of a way of life.

The transition to the form of education in higher educational institutions, the main supporting element in the distribution of study time, as well as the factor ensuring the occurrence of a number of difficulties, are independent works, the constancy and systematicity of which in most cases depends on the successful assimilation of the curriculum.

A kind of acute process in the life and work of students is considered a session of exams. In addition, for the tension of mental activity, the following factors: strong psychological tension (in most students they acquire a negative character); distrust of one's own strength; excessive anxiety, fear of losing one's social status are considered characteristic. The psychophysiological status of educators is constantly changing during the examination session. During this period, such phenomena as exhaustion from intense mental work, lack of time in preparation for exams to strong emotional tension in the waiting period for exams, as well as the renewal of all forces in the body during the passing of exams occur. All this leads to a decrease in workaholicism and the occurrence of depression. Depression, caused by tension and prolonged duration of mental activity, is considered a reversible process, a process that acts as a kind of signal to change the type of mental activity caused by the nature of rest or depression. Increasing mental performance at the expense of functional strain is considered dangerous for the body and leads to severe depression. Strong depression, in turn, requires the implementation of special medical rehabilitation work. Also, severe depression can be the cause that causes serious illnesses.

In general, education, which is organized in higher educational institutions, is characterized by the presence of significant emotional and mental tension arising from situations of hypoxines (muscle and base apparatus, as well as pathological slowness of movement activity) and depression. It is known that the educational process takes place, mainly in a team, in a strictly defined time frame. And in order for the educational process to be successful, it is important for students to study independently at a high level, organize a household lifestyle and rest. At the same time, the effectiveness of Education also depends on the individual activity and its pace, which is organized by the student in the process of cognition, which requires a certain rhythm and systematic course.

According to this aspect, adaptation can be considered a quality that manifests itself in a person in his appearance, ensuring his adaptation to certain conditions or becoming an obstacle. Therefore, adaptation is an innate or acquired individual qualities in a broad sense, mental and physical abilities, personal description, mental and physical perfection, tolerance to life difficulties, passion for education. Adaptation is manifested, first of all, in difficult life situations, in certain test periods, in unfavorable natural climatic conditions. It should also be emphasized once again that adaptation is not only an innate, but also an acquired quality. Accordingly, a high level of Innate adaptation can also subside if unfavorable conditions arise or an unhealthy lifestyle is decided. Likewise, at a low level, congenital adaptation can accelerate the adaptation process that is being carried out. Applying the principles of a healthy lifestyle in practice also helps a lot to ensure the effectiveness of adaptation.

The concept of " healthy lifestyle " expresses the organization of professional, social and household activities that are optimal for the health and development of a person. It also reflects the fact that the activities of the individual are aimed at strengthening social health, its development.

The practical application of the principles of a healthy lifestyle is carried out on the basis of the adoption of socio-economic measures, ensuring the compliance of the individual with their behavior.

The medical and biological basis that ensures a healthy lifestyle is valeology, that is, the science of Health. The basis of the science of valeology lies in the information received during the period of medical examination by a person who organizes professional activities in extreme conditions, including athletes.

The social way of life indicates the choice of life styles by a person in accordance with the basic ideas of valeology. This way of life is necessary in accordance with the important law of valeology, which is based on centuries-old experiences of doctors, educators, psychologists, the biological and social basis of a person. Lifestyle is considered individual and multifaceted, just like the biological and social basis of a person.

Important conditions of a healthy lifestyle are considered:

- 1) movement activity corresponding to the characteristics of the age, biological and social basis of a person;
- 2) comfortable internal and external ecology (full-fledged and moderate nutrition, constant proper cleansing of the body);
- 3) self-destructive behavior (smoking tobacco products, drinking alcohol, drug addiction, etc.).

Moral-value orientation, a spiritual desire to make a decision on a healthy lifestyle indicate that it is possible to comply with these conditions without special self-preparation. Health is necessary for a person to have a first-class need. Satisfying this need should be the most important, priority task facing each state. In order to decide on a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to create such prerequisites that, as a result, it will take a high place in society.

Absolutely necessary, important factors for a healthy lifestyle of students are physical elevation, their age characteristics, the nature of educational activities, household and recreational conditions. This is determined by the following base, the essence and content of the main actions performed by them in everyday life:

- 1) organizational and independent exercise;
- 2) active rest;
- 3) physical labor;
- 4) movement without automatic means.

It should be noted that the influence of physical education and sports is necessary in increasing the body's ability to adapt to the organization of mental activities. Without having a certain volume of base activity, the body will not be able to accumulate energy for its vital activity, resisting moderate daily exertion. The duration of mental labor characteristic of obtaining education in a higher educational institution is manifested in the change in the functioning of all organs and systems. That is:

- 1) the activity of the cardiovascular system changes;
- 2) gas exchange increases;
- 3) hemodynamics occurs in the brain;
- 4) body temperature rises.

Accordingly, mental activity requires a sharp exchange of psychophysiological state in the body.

It is under the system of physical exercises that functional changes occur in the body (blood circulation in the muscles and nutrition of the heart are improved, the amount of erythrocytes and hemoglobin in the blood increases, the workability of the brain cells increases, and they become more resistant to negative influences). Accordingly, the general adaptive capacity of the organism rises to an even higher level. When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it. Of course, physical education exercises do not guarantee protection against various diseases. Studies carried out show that in the upper stages of the higher education system, the manifestation of chronic diseases at a certain time interval (that is, the frequency of diseases) increases. During this period, it can be seen that the main factors affecting the state of students' health are: sleep disorders (24-30 %); eating disorders (10-16 %); decreased employment with exercise (15-30 %).

For this reason, physical education teachers are required to take into account many social factors that influence the lives of students, as well as to focus on them in training.

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